

THEME

Aircraft contaminated air supply: The way forward

OVERVIEW

Aircraft air supplies in all current large passenger transport aircraft (apart from the Boeing 787), utilize non-filtered air (bleed air) drawn from the compressor stage of turbine engines to provide pressurization and breathing air. This design has been utilized since the 1950s and 60s. Synthetic jet engine oils and other fluids in aircraft systems are recognized and known to contaminate the bleed air supply, impacting flight safety, occupational and public health.

This conference followed on from the successful 2005 Air Safety and Cabin Air Quality International Aero Industry Conference held in London in 2005, which concluded that there was a workplace problem resulting in chronic and acute illness amongst flight crew (pilots and cabin crew) and expressed concerns that passengers may also be suffering from similar symptoms to those exhibited by the flight crew.

In the years after the 2005 conference, one cargo airline introduced a cockpit filter unit to filter the air supply to the cockpit. By 2016, with the same company now developing a potential new solution to filter all the air to the passenger cabin and cockpit, a new conference was organized to look at the current understanding of the issue and potential solutions for operators and regulators.

ORGANIZATIONS

The conference principal organizer was the Global Cabin Air Quality Executive (GCAQE), which was established in 2006 as a global coalition of health and safety advocates committed to raising awareness and finding solutions to poor air quality in aircraft. The conference was supported by Pall Aerospace and the following international worker

organizations: the British pilot union (PPU), Unite the Union (Britain's largest trade union), Air Canada Pilot Association (ACPA), Australian Federation of Air Pilots (AFAP), Australian International Pilots Association (AIPA), Association of Professional Flight Attendants (APFA), the International Transport Workers' Federation (ITF) and the University of Stirling. The conference was endorsed by the European Sealing Association, Collegium Ramazzini and the International Joint Policy Committee of the Societies of Epidemiology.

THE CONFERENCE PROGRAM

The conference program of the 2017 International Aircraft Cabin Air Conference included more than 30 oral and video presentations presented by scientists, doctors, pilots, cabin crew, engineers and experts from 11 countries covering a broad spectrum of topics. Most of these presentations are presented in this issue of the journal. The topics include engine design and mechanisms of oil leakage, flight safety, occupational health and safety, regulatory issues, risk management, international actions, reporting, medical and scientific evidence, jet oils, filtration, air quality sensors, legal implications and causation.

The following are a list of the papers presented at the 2017 International Aircraft Cabin Air Conference held at Imperial College London on September 19-20, 2017 in London in the United Kingdom.

Papers were formatted by Dr. Emma King (University of Stirling) and are presented in alphabetical order by corresponding author last name.

Neither the conference organizers or the Journal of Health and Pollution can be held responsible for inaccuracies or errors in any included papers.